

A blind binaural real-time model for listening effort evaluated using continuous subjective listening effort rating

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Abstract – A blind binaural real-time model for estimating listening effort (LE) was developed. The model consists of a binaural front-end, followed by a monaural back-end. As front-end, a novel blind real-time implementation of the binaural speech intelligibility model (BSIM) was developed, which models spatial release from masking by considering binaural unmasking and better-ear listening simultaneously. As the back-end, a neural network was used, which was trained on inputs and outputs of a LE prediction model based on phoneme classification called Listening Effort prediction from Acoustic Parameters (LEAP). A novel method for evaluating binaural real-time models of LE was developed, where simulated scenes with a target speaker and a noise interferer were used, which were either co-located or spatially separated. Dynamic changes were introduced to the scene by abruptly altering the signal-to-noise ratio and/or reverberation time. Participants continuously rated subjectively perceived LE using a slider interface with LE categories, while listening to the scenes via headphones. The model accurately predicted subjective LE, especially changes in signal-to-noise ratio and binaural benefits. It also predicted detrimental effects of reverberation as observed in the experiment, although the impact of reverberation was slightly overestimated. Human response times were estimated for further tweaking the models integration time.

Keywords. Listening effort, Real-time, Spatial hearing

1. Introduction

Estimating speech intelligibility (SI) or listening effort (LE) in real-time can be valuable for several online speech processing applications. For example, a hearing aid device could utilize such estimates to choose the optimal algorithm for varying listening conditions. This study proposes a real-time model to predict LE, along with a novel experimental

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28 assessment method to capture subjectively perceived LE in dynamically changing listening conditions.

29 Regarding the assessment of speech perception, SI has been a subject of research for several decades, while in recent
30 years LE emerged as another relevant speech perception measure [1, 2]. SI and LE are related in a sense that SI is low
31 when LE is high and vice versa. However, while SI might be very high even when noise is present, LE still provides
32 additional information due to the fact that still some effort is required to understand speech. As a result, changes in
33 LE can be observed even if SI is at ceiling [3], making LE more relevant for desired comfortable listening conditions,
34 e.g., in case of a positive signal-to-noise ratio (SNR).

35 Methods of assessing LE can be divided into physiological, subjective and performance-based procedures: Common
36 physiological procedures are electroencephalography (EEG) [4, 5], pupillometry [6, 7] and skin conductance [8].
37 Common subjective procedures are questionnaire assessments [9, 10], ratings on a scale and categorical ratings [11, 12].
38 Performance-based procedures typically include a second (not necessarily auditory) task while performing a listening
39 task, and LE is then operationalized in terms of performance measures in the secondary task [13, 14]. Several models of
40 SI and LE consider that listening with two ears can improve speech recognition, and that those measures are affected
41 by the spatial constellation of sound sources and the listener: Sound coming from a lateralized position arrives earlier
42 at the ipsilateral ear. Likewise, the signal arriving at the contralateral ear is attenuated due to the head-shadowing
43 effect. The difference in time of arrival (or in phase) and in level caused by lateralization is referred to as interaural
44 time differences (ITD) or interaural phase differences (IPD) and interaural level differences (ILD), respectively. The
45 extent of those differences depends on the degree of lateralization and, in general, SI is improved and LE is reduced
46 when speech and noise sources have different ILDs and/or ITDs [15]. Two main factors contribute to this spatial
47 release from masking (SRM): binaural unmasking (BU) and better-ear listening (BEL). BEL occurs when ILDs cause
48 an improvement of the SNR. BU describes an additional unmasking effect that occurs when speech and interferer
49 differ in their ITDs (or IPDs). Note, that BEL and BU can occur to different amounts in different frequency regions.

50 To account for spatial effects in realistic listening scenarios, prediction models for SI and LE should therefore implement
51 BU and/or BEL. One approach to model both effects at once has been proposed with the binaural speech intelligibility
52 model (BSIM) [16, 17], which implemented the Equalization Cancellation (EC) model [18]. The EC model assumes that
53 BU can be modeled by removing ILDs and ITDs of the interferer from both ear signals (Equalization) and subtracting
54 them (Cancellation), yielding an effective SNR improvement due to destructive interference. The BSIM first applies a
55 gammatone filterbank to each ear signal, before applying the EC [18] processing in each filterband independently. Note
56 that due the fact that the EC model is applied only to these bandpass-filtered signals, it has no practical relevance for
57 the predicted masking effect whether the EC processing is implemented using time processing or phase processing. EC
58 processing is done by determining the set of ITDs and ILDs that maximizes the SNR. Then, for each filterband out of
59 both unprocessed ear signals and the EC-processed signal, the one yielding the highest SNR is chosen for determining
60 SI using the speech intelligibility index (SII) [19]. Consequently, the model does not distinguish between BEL and BU,
61 but models them in one common process.

62 A shortcoming of these models is that they are not applicable in real-world scenarios, since they require the use of
63 clean source signals, which are not available to, e.g., a hearing aid. To overcome this limitation, blind models have

64 been proposed that do not require auxiliary information and can derive their predictions based only on the signals
65 actually arriving at the ears. One notable extension to the BSIM in that regard was introduced in [20], where the
66 binaural processing was re-worked to work blindly. However, for estimating SI from the processed, signals the SII [19]
67 was used as a back-end, which still required clean source signals. The model framework was further extended in [21],
68 which proposed a model consisting of blind stages only: the blind BSIM [20] was combined with a blind back-end called
69 Listening Effort prediction from Acoustic Parameters (LEAP) [22–24] instead of the SII. LEAP utilizes a phoneme
70 classifier to make predictions of SI and LE. While the model framework of [21] could, in principle, predict SI and LE
71 from the binaural ear signals alone, it still runs offline and cannot be used to assess SI or LE in real-time, which is the
72 target application of the present study. Therefore, the model framework is further developed, partly simplified, and
73 implemented more efficiently, resulting in a blind and real-time capable prediction model of LE as described in detail
74 below.

75 The real-time model is intended to realistically predict how human LE perception changes in time-varying acous-
76 tic conditions. As far as we know, there is no established method to measure time-varying subjective LE in human
77 listeners. One common way to measure subjective LE is to present a stimulus (e.g., a sentence) and then have the
78 listeners rate the perceived effort on a categorical scale [12]. During the presentation of the stimulus, the acoustic
79 scene (SNR, reverb, spatial source configuration, ...) is usually kept constant. In the present study, we were interested
80 in how perceived LE changes when acoustic parameters change abruptly, and how the predictions of the developed
81 model align with these changes. To this end, a continuous LE assessment method was developed as described below.
82 Conceptually similar continuous psychoacoustic assessment methods were, e.g., used in the context of perceived loud-
83 ness for stimuli altering in level over the course of time [25–27]. Participants were able to continuously rate loudness
84 by either touching a switch next to seven presented loudness categories [25, 26] or using a slider-like interface on a
85 computer screen [27]. However, those experiments were dedicated to investigating the relationship between instantane-
86 ous loudness and overall loudness and not to evaluate continuous model predictions. One example of a real-time
87 assessment of speech stimuli for evaluating a model was proposed in [28], where listeners continuously rated speech
88 quality while time-varying distortions were introduced. The course of speech distortions was pre-generated and called
89 profiles. Each participant heard the same two profiles while rating speech quality continuously using a hardware slider
90 with five quality categories. The subjective ratings were then compared to predictions of a speech quality model with
91 time-varying output computed for time windows shifted along the stimuli.

92 The present study employed a similar concept to investigate perceived LE: time-varying profiles of speech subjected
93 to different amounts of noise and/or reverberation were created in conditions with separated and co-located sound
94 sources. These profiles were continuously rated by listeners using a novel, touchscreen-based interface to investigate
95 the perceptual dynamics of LE. Additionally, reaction times of participants related to sudden changes in noise and
96 reverberation were estimated. The subjective ratings of LE and model predictions were quantitatively compared to
97 assess the model’s prediction accuracy. The analyses also allow to determine necessary integration times for real-time
98 LE evaluations, as a first step towards model-guided hearing devices in the future.

Figure 1. Overview of the front-end model. Horizontal dashed lines indicate a switch between time and spectral domain. The vertical solid line indicates the frequency dependent split of gammatone-filterbands into EC bands and BEL bands. Processing stages marked with * use the overlap-add procedure afterwards.

99 2. Methods

100 2.1. Blind real-time model

101 The model framework of this study was the same as in [21]. A binaural front-end processed the left and right ear
102 signals using an EC mechanism combined with BEL. It produced a binaurally enhanced mono output signal, which
103 was then further processed by a LEAP back-end. However, the model stages had to be modified and re-implemented
104 in order to improve computational efficiency to make it applicable for real-time usage as described below.

105 2.1.1. Model front-end

106 The front-end takes key features of the BSIM version from [20] and implements those for real-time usage in a
107 block processing scheme. An overview of the front-end model can be seen in Figure 1. The model takes the left and
108 right ear signals as blocks of audio $x_t^L[k]$ and $x_t^R[k]$ as inputs. Here, t denotes time frames and k denotes samples. An
109 overlap-add procedure with an overlap of 50% is used for the block processing. Therefore, blocks of audio are of length
110 $2K = 1024$ samples and updated by frames of length $K = 512$, where K is referred to as the hopsize. The model
111 operates at a sampling frequency of 16 kHz leading to a hopsize of 32 ms and blocksize of 64 ms. The left and right
112 ear spectra $X_t^{L/R}[f]$ are computed using the fast Fourier transform (FFT):

$$X_t^{L/R}[f] = \text{FFT} \left\{ w[k] \cdot x_t^{L/R}[k] \right\}. \quad (1)$$

113 Here $w[k]$ denotes a square-root Hann window of length $2K$, which is required, since the same window is used again
114 in the reconstruction phase of the processed signal using the overlap-add procedure. The index f denotes frequency
115 bins. Only half the spectrum up to the Nyquist frequency of 8 kHz is used for efficiency since real-valued signals are
116 processed, resulting in spectra of length $F = \frac{4K}{2} + 1 = 1025$. Before applying the FFT, zero padding to $4K$ is applied
117 to the block of audio $x_t^{L/R}[k]$ to avoid circular convolution artifacts, when doing spectral filtering later.
118 A gammatone filterbank [29] is used since the auditory processing is assumed to work for auditory bandpass filters
119 independently. Filters are applied in the spectral domain instead of time domain for efficiency to obtain the bandpass-
120 filtered spectra $Y_{t,b}^{L/R}[f]$ according to:

$$Y_{t,b}^{L/R}[f] = H_b[f] \cdot X_t^{L/R}[f]. \quad (2)$$

121 $H_b[f]$ denotes the transfer function of the gammatone filterbank from [29], which were calculated from the filter
122 coefficients. The index b denotes auditory filters with $b = 1, \dots, B$, where $B = 29$ is the total number of bandpass
123 filters.

124 The front-end assumes simultaneous EC processing and BEL. Filters with a center frequency below $f_{split} = 1.5$ kHz
125 are processed using the EC procedure, which are 15 filterbands in total. Conversely, filters with a center frequency
126 above f_{split} are processed using BEL selection, which are 14 filterbands in total.

127 For each EC filterband, first, the instantaneous ILD is estimated from the ear spectra $Y_{t,b}^{L/R}[f]$ prior to equalization,
128 as

$$ILD_{t,b}^{inst} = 20 \cdot \log_{10} \left(\sqrt{\frac{\sum_f |Y_{t,b}^L[f]|^2}{\sum_f |Y_{t,b}^R[f]|^2}} \right). \quad (3)$$

129 The actual ILD values $ILD_{t,b}$ are computed by taking the average over the frames of the past 300 ms to simulate
130 the sluggishness of the human binaural processing [30]. The first equalization step is then performed resulting in
131 ILD-equalized spectra $Y_{t,b}^{L,eq1}[f]$ and $Y_{t,b}^{R,eq1}[f]$ for the left and right ear:

$$\begin{aligned} Y_{t,b}^{L,eq1}[f] &= Y_{t,b}^L[f] \cdot 10^{-0.5 \frac{ILD_{t,b}}{20}}, \\ Y_{t,b}^{R,eq1}[f] &= Y_{t,b}^R[f] \cdot 10^{+0.5 \frac{ILD_{t,b}}{20}}. \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

132 Equalization is applied in a symmetric fashion, where the left ear is attenuated by half the ILD, while the right ear is
133 amplified by half the ILD.

134 Then, ITDs are calculated by first estimating the instantaneous IPD for each filterband. For this, the cross power
135 spectral density (CPSD) between the right and left ear $\Phi_{t,b}^{LR}[f]$ is computed bandwise. The frequency bin-wise phase is
136 retrieved by computing the angle of the CPSD and performing phase unwrapping over frequency bins. Instantaneous
137 IPDs are then computed as:

$$IPD_{t,b}^{inst} = \sum_f \angle \Phi_{t,b}^{LR}[f] \frac{|\Phi_{t,b}^{LR}[f]|}{\sum_f |\Phi_{t,b}^{LR}[f]|}, \quad (5)$$

138 where \angle denotes the angle operator to retrieve the bin-wise unwrapped phase.

139 Instantaneous ITDs are then calculated applying the following equation:

$$ITD_{t,b}^{inst} = \frac{IPD_{t,b}^{inst}}{2 \cdot \pi \cdot c f_b}. \quad (6)$$

140 Here $c f_b$ denotes the center frequencies of each auditory filterband. Also, instantaneous ITDs are computed by taking
141 the average over the frames of the past 300 ms resulting in $ITD_{t,b}$. The second equalization step is then performed
142 resulting in fully equalized spectra $Y_{t,b}^{L,eq2}[f]$ and $Y_{t,b}^{R,eq2}[f]$ for the left and right ear according to

$$\begin{aligned} Y_{t,b}^{L,eq2}[f] &= Y_{t,b}^{L,eq1}[f] \cdot e^{-j2\pi f \cdot 0.5 \cdot ITD_{t,b}}, \\ Y_{t,b}^{R,eq2}[f] &= Y_{t,b}^{R,eq1}[f] \cdot e^{+j2\pi f \cdot 0.5 \cdot ITD_{t,b}}. \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

143 ITDs are also equalized in a symmetric fashion. Finally, the cancellation step is performed. Similarly, as done in [20],
144 two approaches are used: The first one is supposed to increase the SNR by means of destructive interference minimizing
145 signal energy of an interfering source by subtracting the equalized ear signals. This is the usual way the EC model [18]
146 is applied. The second one aims to increase the SNR by means of constructive interference maximizing signal energy
147 of a target source by adding the equalized ear signals. Therefore, the signals are computed according to

$$\begin{aligned} Y_{t,b}^{min}[f] &= Y_{t,b}^{L,eq2}[f] - Y_{t,b}^{R,eq2}[f], \\ Y_{t,b}^{max}[f] &= Y_{t,b}^{L,eq2}[f] + Y_{t,b}^{R,eq2}[f]. \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

148 $Y_{t,b}^{min}[f]$ denotes the signal obtained by using the level minimization strategy, while $Y_{t,b}^{max}[f]$ denotes the signal obtained
149 by using the level maximization strategy. The effectiveness of the cancellation step in terms of improved SNR is very
150 dependent on the accuracy of estimated ILDs and ITDs. Also, ITDs of target and interferer, respectively, have to be
151 different for the binaural processing to produce a notable SNR improvement. In order for the minimization strategy
152 to work, estimated ILDs and ITDs have to match the actual ones of the interferer signal. Likewise, the maximization
153 can only lead to an increase in SNR, if estimated ILDs and ITDs are close to the ones of the target signal.

154 The decision which one of the two alternative spectra $Y_{t,b}^{min}[f]$ and $Y_{t,b}^{max}[f]$ is chosen is done in the selection step: Since
155 this is also supposed to work blindly, a measure is needed to determine which EC strategy leads to the greater SNR
156 improvement. For this, a very simple speech modulation detection approach inspired by the speech-to-reverberation
157 modulation energy ratio (SRMR) by [31] is used.

158 Since the SRMR requires analytic signals for each gammatone filterband, the analytic time signal is calculated using
159 the inverse FFT as:

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{y}_t[k] &= \text{iFFT} \{u[f] \cdot Y_t[f]\}, \\ \text{with } u[f] &= \begin{cases} 2 & \text{if } f < F \\ 1 & \text{if } f = F \\ 0 & \text{if } f > F, \end{cases} \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

160 where $u[f]$ denotes an adapted step function centered at the Nyquist frequency at frequency bin F and $\hat{y}_n[k]$ denotes
161 the analytic signal in the time domain of any spectrum $Y_n[f]$. Zero-padding introduced before applying the FFT in
162 Eq. 1 is reversed by cropping the length of $\hat{y}_n[k]$ to $2K$ again.
163 Signal reconstruction is achieved by using the overlap-add method:

$$\hat{y}_{t,b}^{ola}[k] = w[k] \cdot \hat{y}_{t-1,b}[k] + w[k+K] \cdot \hat{y}_{t,b}[k+K]. \quad (10)$$

164 Here $w[k]$ denotes the square-root Hann window, as used in Eq. 1, and $\hat{y}_{t,b}$ any bandpass-filtered analytic signal in
165 time domain of length K .

166 Following the steps of the SRMR [31], the envelope of any analytic signal $\hat{y}_{t,b}^{ola}[k]$ is computed as the absolute value
167 of $\hat{y}_{t,b}^{ola}[k]$. In [31] the envelopes were routed into a modulation filterbank of eight modulation filters, where the lowest
168 four were assumed to represent speech and the highest four assumed to represent noise. We found this approach as
169 too costly in terms of processing speed, which is crucial for an application in real-time. Instead, one modulation filter
170 for detecting modulation typical for speech and one for detecting modulation typical for noise are used. Butterworth
171 bandpass filters of first order are used with a center modulation frequency of 8 Hz for detecting speech modulation
172 and 32 Hz for detecting noise modulation. Both filters have a bandwidth of two octaves each, resulting in a -3 dB
173 crossover of filters at a modulation frequency of 16 Hz.

174 The modulation energy for speech and noise $\epsilon_{t,b}^{s/n}$ is calculated using

$$\epsilon_{t,b}^{s/n} = \sum_k^{m \cdot K} z_{t,b}^{s/n}[k]^2, \quad (11)$$

175 where $z_{t,b}^{s/n}[k]$ represents an internal buffer of 256 ms length, which is updated for every frame. The length was chosen as
176 in [31], to detect speech modulations at modulation frequencies below 8 Hz. Note, that in contrast to [31], where whole
177 signals were processed offline, here, no averaging of modulation energy over time frames was performed. Additionally,
178 since an estimate of the modulation energy is required for each gammatone filterband, no averaging of energy is
179 performed over gammatone filterbands.

180 Finally, a ratio of speech-to-noise modulation energy is calculated:

$$Ratio_{t,b} = \frac{\epsilon_{t,b}^s}{\epsilon_{t,b}^n}. \quad (12)$$

181 The selection whether to use the minimization or maximization strategy is done by checking whichever out of the
182 signals $\hat{y}_{t,b}^{min}[k]$ and $\hat{y}_{t,b}^{max}[k]$ yields a higher ratio for each EC filterband. Similarly, BEL is implemented for each BEL
183 filterband by checking, whichever ear signal out of $\hat{y}_{t,b}^L[k]$ and $\hat{y}_{t,b}^R[k]$ yields a higher ratio. Selected filterband signals
184 are added again using overlap-add according to Eq. 10 for blending consecutive selected frames using a Hann window.
185 Finally, the real parts of selected bands $\hat{y}_{t,b}^{sel}[k]$ are added up to one final output signal $y_t^{out}[k]$, which is the output of
186 the front-end model:

$$y_t^{out}[k] = \sum_b^B \Re\{\hat{y}_{t,b}^{sel}[k]\}. \quad (13)$$

187 2.1.2. Model back-end

188 An end-to-end version of LEAP serves as the back-end. It was developed with the aim of using LEAP in real-time
 189 applications, for which its latency and computational efficiency had to be reduced significantly. To achieve this, a deep
 190 learning model was trained on the outputs of the original LEAP model in order to mimic its behavior of estimating LE.
 191 This way, the time-consuming operations of LEAP are avoided whilst retaining most of its estimation performance.
 192 The neural network architecture shown in Figure 2 was used. It is based on QuartzNet [32] and primarily consists of
 193 one-dimensional convolutions (1D-Conv). At the input layer, mel-spectrograms of $M = 35$ time frames and $N = 100$
 194 frequency bins are fed into the model. They are then processed by a 1D-Conv layer with kernel size of 3 along the time
 195 dimension and a rectified linear unit (ReLU) for activation. Zero padding is used to keep the data shape constant.
 196 The main processing stage consists of time-channel separable convolutions (TCS-Conv), also known as depthwise
 197 separable convolution, which are based on 1D-Conv operations that utilize the channel dimension in order to process
 198 two-dimensional data. TCS-Conv comprise a depthwise convolution (D-Conv) and a pointwise convolution (P-Conv).
 199 First, a D-Conv is applied where for each of the N channels (frequency bins) separate kernels that span across all
 200 M time frames are used. For P-Conv, a single kernel of size 1 that spans across all N channels yields outputs for
 201 each individual time frame. All input and output channels share a weighted connection with a total of N^2 weight
 202 parameters, for a constant number of channels. A single TCS-Conv, as used in this work, requires $MN + N^2 + 2N$
 203 model parameters.

204 In the main processing stage, five blocks, each containing five TCS-Convs with ReLU activation, are applied. The
 205 data shape is retained at $N \times M$ by using zero padding and keeping the number of channels constant for all Conv
 206 operations. An additive skip connection spans from the beginning to the end of each block and contains an extra
 207 P-Conv layer.

208 After these TCS-Conv blocks, feature data are processed by means of a 1D-Conv layer with kernel size 3 without zero
 209 padding. Max pooling is applied such that the time dimension is reduced to a single frame, resulting in a vector of
 210 length N . Next, two fully connected (FC) layers with intermediate ReLU activation reduce the channel dimension to
 211 a single frequency bin, leaving a single scalar value as their output. The output is then scaled to a value between 0
 212 and 1 with a sigmoid function. Mapping this value o with

$$\hat{le} = o \cdot 12 + 1 \quad (14)$$

213 yields the final estimation of listening effort \hat{le} . Overall, the neural network comprises 458,301 trainable model
 214 parameters.

215 The model was trained on mixture signals of German speech and noise. Training and validation sets were generated
 216 in the same way, but with different, non-overlapping splits of the employed data corpora. Speech data were taken from
 217 the German version of CommonVoice 7.0 [33], a crowdsourcing-based corpus with a wide variety of speakers and signal
 218 quality. Since only 8 % of the 1035 hours of data were recorded by female speakers, most of the utterances recorded by
 219 males were discarded in order to achieve a balanced representation of both genders. The data with validated transcripts

Figure 2. Neural network structure of end-to-end LEAP.

220 were used for the training set, those with unvalidated scripts for the validation set. Speechocean King-ASR-187 [34], a
 221 corpus containing about 100 hours of German speech data, was additionally used for the training set. The combined
 222 speech data of both corpora were used a total of three times to reach around 1000 hours of speech data. Noise data were
 223 taken from several different corpora: BBC Sound FX [35] contains a variety of noise types, ranging from human-made
 224 sounds to engine noises. MUSAN [36] comprises 929 noise recordings and more than 42 hours of music of different
 225 genres. The speech data of MUSAN were not used in this work. 997 noise recordings from the Corpus provided as part
 226 of the Deep Noise Supression (DNS) Challenge [37] were also used. Training data were built using all the noise from
 227 the BBC and DNS corpora, as well as 2/3 of the music of MUSAN. The remaining 1/3 of MUSAN’s music as well as
 228 all of its noise data were used for the validation set.

229 Pairs of speech and noise signals were randomly selected and the noise adjusted to match the speech signal’s length.
 230 This was done by truncation if the noise signal was longer than the speech signal or by repetition if it was shorter.
 231 Speech and noise were added at a random SNR of -10, -6, -2, 2, 6, 10, 14, 18, or 22 dB. SNRs were applied using the
 232 active speech level according to ITU P.56 [38]. 28 % of the total data were clean speech without any noise. 95 % of
 233 the data were convolved with one of 60k simulated room impulse responses (RIR), originating from the corpus of [39].
 234 In order to make the model more robust against other disturbances besides noise, the training set was extended with

235 low-resolution MP3-encoded speech. MP3 encoding occurred at 8, 16, 24, 32, 48 and 56 kilobits per second. Half of
 236 the subset’s speech signals were bandpass-filtered between 300 Hz and 3.4 kHz using a second-order butterworth filter
 237 in order to simulate speech transmitted via telephone. Only 48 % of this data were mixed with noise at 2, 6, 10, 14,
 238 18 or 22 dB SNR. Half of the data were convolved with a simulated RIR. In total, the training and validation sets
 239 contained around 1026 hours and 7:39 hours of audio, respectively.

240 Data were fed to the model as mel-spectrograms with non-overlapping frames of 30 ms length and 100 frequency
 241 bins. In order to produce more reliable estimates during real-time usage, each time frame is provided with temporal
 242 context. Besides the current time frame for which the estimation is being made, the 33 preceding frames (0.99 s) and
 243 the following frame are additionally given. By using a future time frame, the system has an algorithmic latency of
 244 at least two frame lengths (60 ms). Training took place with a batch size of $J = 400$ signal frames and lasted for
 245 28 epochs. The mean squared error

$$E_{\text{MSE}} = \frac{1}{J} \sum_{i=i}^J (\hat{l}e_j - l e_j)^2 \quad (15)$$

246 was used as the loss function, with $\hat{l}e_j$ being the estimated LE scores for the j -th signal frame within a batch. The
 247 label $l e_j$ is the desired estimate for the j -th signal frame obtained from the output of the original LEAP model. Model
 248 parameters were optimized using ADAM [40] with an initial learning rate of 10^{-4} .

249 2.2. Real-time subjective evaluations

250 A novel measurement method was developed to assess subjective continuous LE in human participants for dynamic
 251 acoustic scenes to evaluate the model output. Similarly to the work presented in [28], time-continuous profiles were
 252 used. In the current work, profiles only contained abrupt changes and were applied to parameters of a simulated
 253 binaural scene. The simulation was done using the toolbox for acoustic scene creation and rendering (TASCAR) [41],
 254 which implements higher order Ambisonics.

255 The acoustic scene is depicted in Figure 3. It consisted of one target speaker and one noise interferer with a distance
 256 of 10 m to the receiver. The receiver was placed asymmetrically inside a $30 \times 16 \times 9.1$ m³ room to allow for multiple
 257 reflection paths of different lengths. Two spatial conditions were simulated in order to control the effect of binaural
 258 unmasking. Both sources were either placed in front of the receiver (S_0N_0) or rotated around the receiver by 45° in
 259 opposite directions ($S_{-45}N_{+45}$). A general head related transfer function (HRTF) from TASCAR was used. RIRs were
 260 rendered from the scene, so that stimuli could be generated by convolving speech and noise with their respective RIRs.
 261 The German tale “Zwerg Nase” [42] (engl. “Dwarf Nose”) was used as speech material, which had been used prior to
 262 this study in [43], who cut speech pauses to a maximum of 500 ms. The tale was further adapted by splitting the tale
 263 into segments of five minutes each, which will be further referred to as chapters. For each chapter, a questionnaire
 264 was developed consisting each of four questions with each four answer options plus an option “I dont’t know”. As
 265 interferer, ICRA1 noise was used, which is a continuous and nearly unmodulated noise spectrally shaped to correspond
 266 to a male talker [44]. A final stimulus consisted of one chapter each, where different profiles were applied as described

Figure 3. Sketch of the simulated room using TASCAR with dimensions $30 \times 16 \times 9.1$ m³. The receiver was displaced from the middle of the room by -5 m in x direction and -3 m in y -direction and located 1.8 m above ground, while rotated by 22° counter-clockwise. Sound sources were located 10 m in front of the receiver in the co-located condition S_0N_0 or rotated around the receiver by 45° in opposite directions in the spatial condition $S_{-45}N_{+45}$.

267 in the following.

268 Each profile of 300 s length included 30 parameter changes. Those parts, where the modified parameter stayed constant,
 269 are further referred to as sections. One third of all section lengths was set to each of 7, 10, and 13 s, respectively, and
 270 the order of occurrence was randomized to avoid overly predictable time points at which acoustic changes occurred.

271 As scene parameters, SNR and reverberation time T_{60} were chosen, where T_{60} describes the duration in seconds for
 272 the diffuse level to drop by 60 dB after a source stops emitting sound. In order to observe single and combined effects,
 273 they were either adapted while the other parameter stayed constant or parameters were adapted simultaneously. This
 274 led to three distinct profiles: *SNR only*, *T_{60} only* and *SNR+ T_{60}* . For the *SNR only* profile, only additive noise was
 275 added without any reverberation. For the *T_{60} only* profile, no noise was added and speech was reverberated with RIRs
 276 of different T_{60} values. Four seconds of audio before the actual section were used when convolving with RIRs and
 277 discarded afterwards, if reverberation was applied. That way, reverberation was approximately fully built up in the
 278 section of interest. For the *SNR+ T_{60}* profile, both noise and reverberation were used. While the temporal sequence
 279 of SNRs and T_{60} values was randomized differently for the three profiles, the exact same temporal pattern was used
 280 within each profile for the S_0N_0 and the $S_{-45}N_{+45}$ conditions. The two spatial setups thus differed only in the spatial
 281 source configuration, while all other parameters and their temporal changes were the same. This was done to be able
 282 to analyze the role of the binaural benefit independently from temporal parameter changes. Additionally, a training
 283 profile was used, where for every section one of the six profiles was selected at random and parameters adapted the
 284 respective way. In this case, the tale “Der Jäger und der Zwergenprinz” [45] (engl. “The hunter and the dwarven
 285 prince”) spoken by a different male talker was used, where the same modifications as for the other tale were applied
 286 by [43].

287 When generating profiles, parameters were drawn at random from uniform distributions, which can be seen in Table 1.
 288 Changes of SNR were applied by amplifying speech by half of the SNR and attenuating noise by half of the SNR.
 289 That way, the overall level was reduced compared to applying the SNR to one signal type only, preventing a biased
 290 perceived subjective LE due to high loudness. An SNR of 0 dB corresponded to a speech and noise level of 65 dB SPL

Table 1. Distributions used for generating each profile. Ranges are displayed as start : step size : end. Note that gains marked with * indicate actual gain increases to the speech signal, while for the other profiles it symbolizes a change in SNR. SNR is applied by amplifying speech by half of the SNR and by attenuating noise by half of the SNR. A T_{60} of 0 s indicates an anechoic setting. The time courses of the parameter changes over time are also displayed in the results sections.

Profile	SNR or Gain /dB	T_{60} /s
SNR only (S_0N_0)	-12:3:+12	0
T_{60} only (S_0)	+6*	0,1,3,5
SNR+ T_{60} (S_0N_0)	-12:3:+12	0,1,3,5
SNR only ($S_{-45}N_{+45}$)	-12:3:+12	0
T_{60} only (S_{-45})	+6*	0,1,3,5
SNR+ T_{60} ($S_{-45}N_{+45}$)	-12:3:+12	0,1,3,5

291 each. Furthermore, random overall level roving of each section by between -3 and 3 dB (step size 1dB) was applied to
 292 avoid a bias of perceived subjective LE due to constant loudness of stimuli.

293 This procedure produced six fixed 300 s long profiles of temporal changes in SNR and/or T_{60} that were used for
 294 each participant. In order to minimize systematic training effects, the six profiles were assigned to each participant in
 295 random order. However, since the chapters of the story used as speech material needed to be presented in chronological
 296 order for the tale to make sense, the chapters were always presented in the same order. This meant that each participant
 297 listened to different combinations of speech and profiles. The only exception was the training stimulus, which consisted
 298 of the same speech stimulus combined with the training profile.

299 For gathering real-time feedback from participants, an application was developed, allowing to continuously assess
 300 perceived subjective LE using a slider interface that was accessible via network using a smartphone. The slider covered
 301 a range of 1 to 14 effort scale categorical units (ESCU) in accordance with [12]. Values were not visible, but 6 categories
 302 ranging from “effortless” (1 ESCU) to “extreme effort” (13 ESCU) were displayed plus an additional category “noise
 303 only” (14 ESCU) for cases, where speech was not audible. As additional visual feedback, the background color of the
 304 slider interface changed depending on the slider position ranging from green (1 ESCU) to red (14 ESCU) on the HSV
 305 color scale by [46]. A Dell Latitude 5431 Notebook connected to an RME Babyface sound card with Sennheiser HD650
 306 headphones was used. As smartphone, a Sharp Aquos D10 was provided. A network was accessed using a Fritzbox
 307 7490 router. The measurement was conducted in a soundproof booth. The equipment was calibrated using Brüel &
 308 Kjær hardware including a Type 4153 artificial ear, a Type 2669 preamplifier and a Type 2610 measuring amplifier
 309 calibrated with a Type 4231 sound calibrator.

310 Thirteen female and seven male participants with a mean age of 27.7 years and standard deviation of 5.5 years took
 311 part in this study. They had normal audiometric thresholds (PTA4 <20dB HL), were self-proclaimed German native
 312 speakers and had no red-green color blindness, which would have interfered with the changing background color of
 313 the slider app. Only three participants reported to ever have taken part in an experiment where LE was assessed.
 314 Participants received an instruction sheet and were not allowed to ask questions about how to do the measurement
 315 to avoid reproducibility issues. Participants did not take any breaks during the measurement although allowed by
 316 the instruction sheet. Before each chapter, they were asked to press a play button when they were ready. After each
 317 chapter, they were asked to turn over the corresponding questionnaire sheet regarding the contents of the just played

Figure 4. Median subjective (blue) and predicted (gray) LE time courses in ESCU for S_0N_0 (top panel) and $S_{-45}N_{+45}$ (middle panel) and the presented *SNR only* profile (bottom panel). LE is displayed with IQR displayed as a patch.

318 chapter to assess if participants were still attentive. They had to correctly answer at least 50% of the questions to not
 319 being excluded post measurement. This led to the exclusion of one male participant, so that 19 participants in total
 320 were eligible to be analyzed.

321 3. Results

322 3.1. Temporal patterns

323 The time courses of assessed subjective LE in ESCU plotted as median over participants with inter quartile range
 324 (IQR) alongside model predictions are shown in Figures 4 to 6. In each figure, from top to bottom the course of LE for
 325 S_0N_0 is shown, then LE for $S_{-45}N_{+45}$ and lastly the presented profile. The median LE and IQR for model predictions
 326 was calculated over the combinations of each profile and the six chapters. Figure 4 shows the time courses for the
 327 *SNR only* profile. Subjective LE ratings varied strongly over time, with median LE values ranging from below 3 ESCU
 328 (“very little effort”) to 13 ESCU (“extreme effort”). Within each section (see section transitions in bottom panel), LE
 329 ratings were rather stable, suggesting that listeners did not re-adjust their slider position a lot after having adapted
 330 to a change in SNR. As expected, changes in SNR caused changes in LE rating in a contrary manner (note that the
 331 SNR scale is inverted). There appeared to be a systematic delay in the response of the LE ratings after each section

Figure 5. Median subjective (blue) and predicted (gray) LE time courses in ESCU for S_0 (top panel) and S_{-45} (middle panel) and the presented T_{60} *only* profile (bottom panel). LE is displayed with IQR displayed as a patch.

332 transition, which is analyzed further below. The subjective LE was often lower in the spatially separated condition
 333 by up to 3 ESCU compared to the co-located condition. The spatial benefit is also analyzed in more detail below.
 334 Predicted LE values followed a similar pattern with strong changes of predicted LE at section boundaries. Within each
 335 section, predicted LE varied more than the subjective median ratings. LE predictions closely matched median ratings
 336 for intermediate LE, and slightly over- and underestimated median ratings by about 1-2 ESCU at low and high LE,
 337 respectively. For the T_{60} *only* profile (Figure 5) the course of subjectively perceived and predicted LE followed the
 338 course of the T_{60} parameter. In contrast to the *SNR only* profile, the range of LE was decreased, where most of the
 339 time the upper limit was at 9 ESCU. Also, the lateralization of the speech source did not lead to obvious differences
 340 in LE. However, the predicted LE always exceeded subjective LE throughout the stimulus in a range of 1-4 ESCU.

341 Figure 6 shows the results for the $SNR+T_{60}$ profile. Here, the relationship between both parameters and subjective
 342 as well as predicted LE was more complicated. In the most extreme cases, high SNR in combination with low T_{60}
 343 led to the lowest subjective and predicted LE, respectively. This can be seen for example at 50 s, where an SNR of
 344 6 dB and a T_{60} of 0 s were used. Conversely, low SNR in combination with high T_{60} led to the highest subjective and
 345 predicted LE, respectively. This can be seen for example around 130 s, where an SNR of -12 dB and a T_{60} of 5 s were
 346 used. The model again overestimated LE for sections with decreased SNR and increased reverberation, which can be
 347 seen for instance around 100 s and 200 s.

Figure 6. Median subjective (blue) and predicted (gray) LE time courses in ESCU for S_0N_0 (top panel) and $S_{-45}N_{+45}$ (middle panel) and the presented $SNR+T_{60}$ profile (bottom panel). LE is displayed with IQR displayed as a patch.

348 3.2. Steady-state responses

349 The temporal courses of LE ratings suggested that listeners required some time to converge towards a position
 350 on the slider after each section change, and that they did not strongly re-adjust their ratings until the next section
 351 change. In other words, the median ratings at the end of each section should reflect the listeners' steady-state responses
 352 and should be comparable to ratings one would obtain in classic, non-real-time assessments where listeners rate LE
 353 after they heard the stimuli. To obtain a stable LE value for each section, a temporal mean was calculated over the
 354 last 2 s for each section for all participants and the model. This value of 2 s was determined experimentally, since
 355 low variance of LE was observed in the last 2 s. Afterwards, a median over all participants and model predictions
 356 was calculated for each section. Additionally, a linear regression analysis was performed for each profile as well as all
 357 profiles combined using an ordinary least squares model. A scatter plot displaying the relationship of predicted and
 358 subjective LE is shown in Figure 7. Here, the median of predicted LE is compared against the median of subjective
 359 LE in ESCU for each section and all profiles. The shape and color of each data point indicate the underlying profile.
 360 A regression line alongside the results of the linear regression analysis over all data points is shown in the top left
 361 corner. The results of the linear regression analysis for each individual profile can be seen in Table 2. For the profiles
 362 adapting only one parameter, a high coefficient of determination R^2 above 0.9 could be observed except for the *SNR*
 363 *only* in $S_{-45}N_{+45}$, which was at 0.83. R^2 values for the $SNR+T_{60}$ profiles in S_0N_0 and $S_{-45}N_{+45}$ amounted to 0.84

Figure 7. Median of predicted LE plotted against the median of subjective LE in ESCU for each section. Data points are grouped by the six different profiles. The black line represents the linear regression line, while the results of the linear regression analysis are displayed in the top left corner.

364 and 0.81, respectively. The slope of the linear regression line was far below 1.0 except for the condition T_{60} only
365 S_0 , while the bias across profiles varied in a range of 1.95 to 4.60 ESCU. While the root mean square error (RMSE) for
366 all profiles was at 1.0 ESCU, it was notably lower for individual profiles.

367

368 3.3. Binaural benefit

369 To analyze the binaural benefit, the same steady-state LE values calculated above were used. For each participant
370 and section ending, subjective LE values for spatially separated sources were subtracted from subjective LE values for
371 co-located sources. The same was done for the model predictions. The results grouped by SNR and T_{60} are displayed
372 as violin plots in Figure 8. IQRs are shown as boxes, where the white line displays the median and whiskers are

Table 2. Results of a linear regression analysis performed on subjective and predicted LE for each profile as well as all profiles combined. Columns show values for R^2 , slope as well as bias of the regression line and the RMSE.

Profile	R^2	Slope	Bias /ESCUCU	RMSE /ESCUCU
SNR only (S_0N_0)	0.95	0.76	2.18	0.74
T_{60} only (S_0)	0.92	1.06	2.05	0.69
SNR+ T_{60} (S_0N_0)	0.84	0.59	4.60	0.84
SNR only ($S_{-45}N_{+45}$)	0.83	0.72	1.95	0.96
T_{60} only (S_{-45})	0.94	0.81	2.78	0.50
SNR+ T_{60} ($S_{-45}N_{+45}$)	0.81	0.64	3.92	0.87
All	0.87	0.73	2.85	1.0

Figure 8. Spatial release of LE for participants (blue) and the model (gray) due to lateralization of sound sources for the *SNR only* (upper panel) and *T₆₀ only* (lower panel) profiles visualized as violin plots with box plots. Values are grouped by SNR and *T₆₀* values, respectively. Black boxes display IQRs, where the median is indicated as a white line inside. Whiskers are added as black lines. Note that for the *T₆₀ only* profile and a *T₆₀* of 0 s no box and whiskers were drawn since most data points are at 0 ESCU.

373 added as lines. Note, that only data from the profiles adapting single parameters are shown, since for *SNR+T₆₀* not
 374 all possible combinations of SNR and *T₆₀* values were used. In case of the SNR being adapted, the median binaural
 375 LE benefit for participants and the model decreased with increasing SNR. For the lowest presented SNR of -12 dB,
 376 median values for participants and the model amounted to 2.5 ESCU, respectively. The median LE benefit dropped

377 to 0 ESCU for participants as well as for the model at the highest SNR.

378 In case of the speech source being lateralized to -45° for the T_{60} *only* profile, the median LE release was at around
 379 0 ESCU for participants regardless of presented T_{60} . In contrast to that, the median predicted LE release by the model
 380 amounted to about -1 ESCU, indicating a higher LE being induced by the lateralization. However, with increasing
 381 T_{60} , the predicted spatial release of LE increased to about 1 ESCU for a T_{60} of 5 s.

382 3.4. Response times to abrupt changes

383 The cross-correlation between each participant’s time-varying LE assessments and profiles was calculated for each
 384 of the six profiles to estimate the response times of participants similar to [28]. The point in time of each cross
 385 correlation peak was determined to obtain the delay of participants.

386 The results can be seen as violin plots in Figure 9. Median response times were determined in a range from 1.54
 387 to 2.16 s, while overall response times appeared to be greatest for the $SNR+T_{60}$ profile and lowest for the T_{60} *only*
 388 profiles by a slight margin compared to the response times for the SNR *only* profiles. A Shapiro-Wilk test revealed
 389 that not all distributions were normally distributed. Therefore, a Kruskal-Wallis test was applied, which returned that
 390 at least one distribution differed significantly from one other distribution ($H=23.47$, $p<0.001$). Post-hoc Dunn’s tests
 391 with Bonferroni correction revealed that in S_0N_0 response times for the $SNR+T_{60}$ profile differed significantly from the
 392 one for the T_{60} *only* profile at a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$. Response times for the $SNR+T_{60}$ profile in $S_{-45}N_{+45}$
 393 differed significantly at a level of $\alpha = 0.01$ from the ones for the T_{60} *only* profile regardless of spatial configuration.

394 4. Discussion

395 The time courses in Figure 4 to 6 indicate that predicted LE is in line with subjective LE. This is supported by
 396 the high correlation values and fairly low RMSE values shown in Table 2. The main discrepancy was that the model

Figure 9. Distribution of estimated response times in seconds for all six profiles. Significant differences are indicated with * and ** for significance levels of $\alpha = 0.05$ and $\alpha = 0.01$, respectively.

397 overestimates LE in the presence of reverberation.

398 On the one hand, the model might overestimate the effect of reduced ITDs and ILDs. On the other hand, the back-end
 399 might not be able to handle the type of reverberation produced by TASCAR [41], although it was trained on a very
 400 large RIR dataset. The outputs of the LEAP model, which was used to train the proposed back-end, might also be
 401 biased with regard to reverberation. A short analysis was performed to find the origin of the mismatch, where the
 402 end-to-end LEAP model was replaced by the original version, and both LEAP versions were also run separately for
 403 each ear to obtain a better-ear prediction without binaural preprocessing. It was found that, in general, the overesti-
 404 mation decreased when using the original LEAP version, while it decreased further when running the LEAP version
 405 on the better ear signal only. Those results suggest that both the blind BSIM front-end and the end-to-end LEAP
 406 back-end contributed to the overestimation of LE in reverberant conditions. The proposed model could further be
 407 extended to incorporate hearing loss and adapted to being able to handle speech masking, which currently would lead
 408 to underestimated LE due to the back-end favoring the presence of speech in general.

409 Apart from that, the low slope values combined with a positive bias suggest that the model tends to avoid to output
 410 extremely low and extremely high ESCU values. For high LE, this can be partially explained by the fact that par-
 411 ticipants were able to rate LE on a scale of up to 14 ESCU, while the model was trained on a scale of up to only
 412 13 ESCU. However, as can be seen in the time courses in Figure 4 to 6, the median subjective LE does very rarely
 413 exceed values of 13 ESCU.

414 While R^2 is very high for profiles adapting just one parameter, R^2 is notably lower for the $SNR+T_{60}$ profile.

415 As shown in Figure 8, the separation of speech and noise for the *SNR only* profile led to a binaural benefit in subjective
 416 LE as well as predicted LE, which increases with decreasing SNR. The data for participants for the *T₆₀ only* profile,
 417 where only one speech source was presented, support this interpretation, since only diffuse reverberation was present.
 418 Surprisingly, here the model predicts increased LE by about 1 ESCU in the anechoic setting if the speech source is
 419 lateralized. Furthermore, a very subtle binaural benefit of about 1 ESCU is predicted for high reverberation.

420 When comparing the results for subjective and predicted LE to the findings from [21], the overall binaural benefit
 421 in ESCU appears to be smaller. They observed subjective LE ratings for speech in noise using an American matrix
 422 sentence test [47]. Subjective LE ratings were tracked for static SNR values ranging from -25 to +10 dB for different
 423 spatial settings. Here, the speech source was located in front of the receiver and the noise source was moved to different
 424 positions, which differs from the procedure in this work. The S_0N_{100} condition in [21] is the closest to the $S_{-45}N_{+45}$
 425 in this study judging by the angular distance between the speech and noise sources. Comparing the difference in LE
 426 for the S_0N_{100} and S_0N_0 conditions in [21] yields a binaural benefit of about 6 ESCU at an SNR of -10 dB. This is a
 427 huge difference to the binaural benefit of 2.5 ESCU at an even smaller SNR of -12 dB in this study.

428 The response times for judging LE appeared to be a little higher when SNR and T_{60} were adapted simultaneously,
 429 while the average response time was just below 2 s. Compared to the findings of continuous speech quality in [28],
 430 where response times around 1 s were observed, this is a large difference. A comparable response time was only achieved
 431 by very few participants (Figure 9). Nevertheless, there are some notable differences between [28] and the procedure
 432 described here. A simple explanation could be that speech quality degradation caused by signal distortion is faster to

433 rate than induced LE due to changes in SNR and T_{60} . In some cases, parameter changes could have had a very little
434 effect, so that participants reacted slower. This can be seen for example for SNR changes of just 3 dB in Figure 4 or
435 for changes in T_{60} of 3 s and of 5 s in Figure 5. Another reason for the difference in response times could have been
436 caused by the different groups of participants. In [28] participants were recruited from the lab and thus probably had
437 experience with speech quality measurements or comparable experiments. Therefore, it might have been easier for
438 them to rate speech quality. Participants recruited in this study have mostly not taken part in any hearing experiment
439 evolving around LE, which is why they might have had to come up with an idea, how to rate LE over the course of the
440 experiment. Another factor might have been the use of abrupt parameter changes only, while in [28] gradual parameter
441 changes were observed as well. While the occurrence of an abrupt change in this study was unpredictable, gradual
442 changes could be easier to follow once the onset of such a parameter change is noticed. This could have lowered the
443 average response times estimated by calculating the cross-correlation of subjective LE courses and the profiles. Lastly,
444 the overall mental load throughout the experiment from this study could have been higher, since participants had to
445 also pay attention to the story contents and stimuli of 5 min were considerably longer than the 40 s stimuli from [28].
446 The response times estimated in this study could be used to determine smoothing constants of the model outputs.
447 However, the actual human processing time to perceive LE is still unknown, since the response time also includes the
448 delay to transmit the percept of LE on the slider interface.

449 5. Conclusions

450 This work introduced a blind binaural model for predicting LE, which runs in real-time.
451 A method for assessing subjective continuous LE was introduced to evaluate the proposed model. The presented
452 lightweight and easy setup could in theory be used for in-the-field experiments with focus on ecological validity.
453 The results showed that the model can quite accurately predict subjective LE for changes in SNR. However, the effect
454 of reverberation is slightly overestimated.

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461 Conflicts of interest

462 The authors declare no conflict of interest.

463 **Data availability statement**

464 The experimental data will be made available on request. The code of the binaural BSIM model will be published
465 and the link added here.

466 **Ethical approval**

467 All participants received hourly compensation and gave informed consent for their participation in the experiments.
468 The methods were approved by the ethics committee of the University of Oldenburg (protocol Drs.-Nr. 04/2018).

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